

A conceptual evaluation of the use of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ for attaining carbon capture rates of 99% in the calcium looping process

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ABSTRACT

Calcium looping (CaL), typically capable of reducing CO_2 emissions by approximately 90%, is a technology well suited to capturing CO_2 emissions from a wide array of industrial processes. An approach in which $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ is injected into the carbonator to increase the carbon capture efficiency of the CaL process to 99% was evaluated in this study using a one-and-a-half-dimensional reactor model. The effect of several key parameters was considered, including the injection flow rate, injection elevation, and the formation rate of CO_2 in the freeboard of the carbonator due to the combustion of char particles elutriated from the calciner. The main finding was that capture rates of 99% appear attainable, given that enough $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ is injected and that the injection occurs at a suitable location, i.e., the sorbent is allowed sufficient residence time in the reactor.

1. Introduction

Carbon capture, utilisation, and storage (CCUS) technologies are recognised as vital for addressing climate change and achieving short-term emissions targets (IPCC, 2018; IEA, 2021), especially for decarbonisation of the so-called hard-to-abate sectors (IEA, 2020). Although no consensus exists on what constitutes a sufficient capture rate, it has been suggested that emissions should only be considered “abated” when 90–95% or more of the CO_2 emissions are captured (Bataille et al., 2023). Calcium looping (CaL) is a carbon capture technology well suited to decarbonising hard-to-abate industrial processes, such as cement production and power generation (Abanades et al., 2015; Dziejarski et al., 2023). However, since the capture rate of CaL typically reaches around 90% (Arias et al., 2013; Dieter et al., 2014; Hilz et al., 2017), methods to further improve the capture rate may be needed to meet future requirements.

The standard calcium looping process consists of two interconnected circulating fluidised bed (CFB) reactors, the carbonator and the calciner, which are operated at atmospheric pressure and use a calcium-based sorbent as their bed material (Shimizu et al., 1999; Abanades et al., 2015). The carbonator captures carbon dioxide (CO_2) from flue gases in a reaction with calcium oxide (CaO), forming calcium carbonate (CaCO_3) as given by Eq. (1):

The calciner regenerates the sorbent by heating it to a higher temperature, decomposing the CaCO_3 back into CaO , and releasing a

concentrated stream of CO_2 for capture. The operating conditions in the reactors are determined by the $\text{CaO}-\text{CO}_2$ equilibrium curve: a temperature of 900 °C is needed to calcine the sorbent in a stream of pure CO_2 , whereas in the carbonator, reducing the CO_2 concentration to 1.2%_{vol} requires a temperature of 650 °C (Abanades et al., 2015). For typical flue gases with CO_2 concentrations of 10–15%-v, this corresponds to carbon capture efficiencies of around 90%. Carbon capture efficiency is defined as

$$E_{\text{CO}_2} = 1 - \frac{F_{\text{CO}_2,\text{out}}}{F_{\text{CO}_2,\text{in}}} \quad (2)$$

Reducing the operating temperature of the carbonator increases the maximum CO_2 capture efficiency, as dictated by the $\text{CaO}-\text{CO}_2$ equilibrium. However, this reduces reaction rates and the CO_2 -carrying capacity of the sorbent (Dieter et al., 2014; Criado et al., 2018), increases energy consumption (Arias et al., 2022b), and may reduce the thermal efficiency of the process, as heat is available at a lower temperature in the carbonator. Nevertheless, a number of ideas have been proposed to improve the carbon capture efficiency of the CaL process. Operating the carbonator with a dense bed and low gas velocity at temperatures above 600 °C has enabled capture rates of 95% (Diego and Arias, 2020; Fang et al., 2009a). Higher capture rates are generally attainable in such conditions, as higher inventories lead to higher residence times and higher conversions. However, decreasing the gas velocity increases the required cross-sectional area of the reactor and hence its construction cost (Abanades et al., 2015). Another well-known

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Nomenclature**Greek Symbols**

$\Delta H_{298\text{ K}}$	Reaction enthalpy at 298 K [J mol ⁻¹]
η	hydrodynamic parameter [-]
ρ	density [kg m ⁻³]

Roman Symbols

a	decay constant [m ⁻¹]
A_c	cross-sectional area [m ²]
A_m	specific surface area [m ² kg ⁻¹]
C	concentration [mol m ⁻³]
c	empirical calibration coefficient [-]
E	energy [J]
E_{CO_2}	carbon capture efficiency [mol mol ⁻¹]
F	molar flow [mol s ⁻¹]
h	heat transfer coefficient [W m ⁻² K ⁻¹]
K	decay constant [m ⁻¹]
k	rate constant [unit varies]
k_0	pre-exponential factor [unit varies]
K_{WGS}	equilibrium constant for the water–gas shift reaction [-]
M	molar mass [kg mol ⁻¹]
m	mass [kg]
n	quantity [mol]
Q	energy flow [W]
q_m	mass flow rate [kg s ⁻¹]
R	universal gas constant, 8.314 J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹
r	reaction rate [kg s ⁻¹]
T	temperature [K]
t	time [s]
u	velocity [m s ⁻¹]
V	volume [m ³]
W	mass fraction [kg kg ⁻¹]
X	molar fraction [mol mol ⁻¹]
X_{max}	CO ₂ carrying capacity of a sorbent particle [mol mol ⁻¹]
z	elevation from the grid [m]
Z_e	elevation at the centre of the exit opening [m]

Subscripts

adv	advection
bm	bed material
Ca	all Calcium-based species
calc	calcination
carb	carbonation
circ	circulation
dehy	dehydration
desu	desulphation
dirs	direct sulphation
disp	dispersion
eq	equilibrium
g	gas
HT	heat transfer

i	index, control volume
j	index, species
pn	pneumatic transport conditions
r	index, reaction
s	solids
sulph	sulphation
t	terminal
tot	total
WGS	water-gas shift

concepts focus on reactivation strategies to increase the CO₂-carrying capacity of the sorbent, such as re-carbonation in a CO₂-rich atmosphere (Lysikov et al., 2007; Diego et al., 2014; Valverde et al., 2014), or the addition of an intermediate hydration step (Hughes et al., 2004; Phalak et al., 2013; Li et al., 2016) where CaO is hydrated to produce calcium hydroxide (Ca(OH)₂), which is then used in the carbonator to capture CO₂ following the reaction

Drop-tube experiments indicate that highly reactive Ca(OH)₂ can be carbonated to a maximum degree of conversion of approximately 0.7 mol/mol in just a few seconds, which is significantly higher than what is attainable by CaO derived from CaCO₃ (Arias et al., 2022b,a). Concepts in which Ca(OH)₂ is used as the sorbent have been proposed by Phalak et al. (2013) and also by Fierro et al. (2022), Criado and Arias (2022). In the latter two approaches, the high reactivity and CO₂-carrying capacity of Ca(OH)₂ would allow the design of entrained flow reactors targeting capture rates of 90–95% (Arias et al., 2022a). In a recent development, Arias et al. (2024) have tested a strategy based on operating the CaL system with a high make-up flow of limestone and with the top region of the carbonator at a temperature below 550 °C. The resulting high CO₂-carrying capacity of the sorbent, combined with a sufficiently low temperature, has allowed them to reach carbon capture efficiencies above 99%.

The configuration studied in this paper is a hybrid design, where the bulk of CO₂ entering the carbonator is captured in the lower region of the reactor by CaO coming from the calciner and Ca(OH)₂ is used as a supplementary sorbent to further increase the carbon capture efficiency of the carbonator (Abanades and Arias, 2023). The bottom part of the carbonator is operated at a temperature close to 650 °C, where the CO₂ concentration quickly drops close to equilibrium, or 1.2%-v. The top region of the carbonator is cooled to a temperature close to 550 °C, corresponding to an equilibrium CO₂ concentration below 0.1%-v, and a fine Ca(OH)₂ powder is injected into this cooler zone. There, it is entrained and partly carbonated by the CO₂ remaining in the gas, bringing residual CO₂ concentration close to equilibrium in a few seconds and allowing the carbonator to reach carbon capture efficiencies of 99%.

Ca(OH)₂ injection has been simulated in Secomandi et al. (2024) and the results reported support the understanding that capture efficiencies close to 99% would be achievable. However, the simulated reactors were operated under partial-load conditions, with a relatively low gas velocity (2.6 m/s) and a cool temperature profile (550–650 °C) in the carbonator. As the gas velocity decreases, the reduced circulation of solids between the reactors reduces the sensible heat input into the carbonator, thus facilitating its cooling. Achieving similar capture efficiencies at higher loads is expected to be more challenging, but higher gas throughputs are generally more economical (Abanades et al., 2015) and thus to be preferred.

A phenomenon not considered in the previous study is the potential formation of CO₂ in the freeboard of the carbonator. In commercial power-generating CFB units, char particles are entrained, separated in

approach is the introduction of steam into the carbonator atmosphere, as the presence of steam is known to accelerate the carbonation reaction (Donat et al., 2012; Dieter et al., 2013; Li et al., 2016). Other

the cyclone, and recirculated to the bottom of the reactor multiple times before being completely consumed (Basu, 2006). In a calcium looping unit, the solids entrained in the calciner are circulated to the carbonator, and these solids can be expected to include some char. Gao et al. (2014) found that char combustion in the carbonator caused an increase in CO₂ concentration of 0.5–4%v in their laboratory-scale reactor system. Char particles circulated to the carbonator can be partially oxidised by residual oxygen in the gas, to form CO and CO₂, before being entrained again. While the kinetics of CO combustion are relatively slow at temperatures such as those found in the carbonator (Yetter et al., 1986), the presence of water vapour, which is both a component of the fluidisation gas as well as a product of the decomposition of Ca(OH)₂, may accelerate the conversion of CO into CO₂ via the water–gas shift reaction. The carbon capture efficiency of the reactor may be impaired by the CO₂ formed in the freeboard of the carbonator since it bypasses the dense bed, where most of the CO₂ is captured. Consequently, not only the total amount of CO₂ formed is of interest, but also the local formation rates across the reactor volume.

In this work, a one-and-a-half-dimensional reactor model is used to examine a novel method proposed by Abanades and Arias (Abanades and Arias, 2023) in which Ca(OH)₂ is injected into the cooler top part of the carbonator to boost the carbon capture efficiency of the process. Since it is a new method, there is a lack of knowledge for how the process would perform under different design parameters, such as the elevation and mass flow of the Ca(OH)₂ injection. In addition to a sensitivity analysis of parameters related to the injection, the study covers strategies to control the temperature of the carbonator and the effect that the combustion of char in the carbonator could have on the overall carbon capture efficiency. The objective of this study is to offer insight into the expected behaviour of a calcium looping system when Ca(OH)₂ is injected into the carbonator as a supplementary sorbent by providing an understanding of the flow rates and elevations best suited for high capture efficiencies. This information supports further development of the concept and the design of future reactors and experiments.

2. Methodology

Due to the high aspect ratio of the reactors, variation in the cross-sectional plane of the reactors is expected to be small, and so the conceptual evaluation of the hydroxide injection was done by building a 1.5D reactor model of the La Pereda pilot plant (Arias et al., 2013) and simulating how the process would respond to the addition of calcium hydroxide injection. The CaL model was built in the Simulink environment and consists of two instances of a 1.5D reactor model, which are interconnected such that the solids leaving the calciner serve as input for the carbonator and vice versa. Ca(OH)₂ is injected in the carbonator as fine (10 μm) particles and is assumed to leave the cyclone with the gas stream, as illustrated in Fig. 1.

2.1. 1.5D reactor model

The 1.5D reactor model used in this study is based on the model published by Ylätaalo et al. (2012), which is a transient, one-dimensional model used to simulate CFB reactors. The reactor is divided vertically into finite volumes for which time-dependent conservation equations of mass and energy are solved, and radially into a core region and a wall layer in order to simulate the internal circulation of solids that characterises CFBs. The simulation procedure is illustrated in Fig. 2.

The rate of change of the mass of a species j in control volume i is given by:

$$\frac{dm_{j,i}}{dt} = \sum_{in} q_{m,j,i} - \sum_{out} q_{m,j,i} + \sum_{reaction} r_{j,i}, \quad (4)$$

where $q_{m,j}$ is the mass flow rate of a given species j , and positive values of r_j represent the mass of species j produced by a chemical reaction

per unit time. Similarly, the energy balance of a discrete volume i is given by:

$$\frac{dE_i}{dt} = \sum_{solid} Q_{adv,i} + \sum_{gas} Q_{adv,i} + \sum_{solid} Q_{disp,i} + \sum Q_{HT,i} + \sum_{reaction} Q_{r,i}, \quad (5)$$

where Q_{adv} is heat transfer due to advection, Q_{disp} is heat dispersion between neighbouring control volumes as obtained by applying the central difference method to Fick's law of diffusion, Q_{HT} is heat transferred to heat absorbing surfaces, and Q_r is reaction heat. Heat transfer between the solids and water walls is calculated from the correlation of Dutta and Basu (2002) for the convective heat transfer coefficient:

$$h_{HT,i} = 5\rho_{s,i}^{0.391} T_i^{0.408} \quad (6)$$

where the temperature is in degrees Celsius. For wing walls inside the furnace, the heat transfer coefficient is reduced by 25% (Basu, 2006). The conservation equations are solved by the ordinary differential equation (ODE) solvers available in Simulink.

2.1.1. Hydrodynamic submodel

In order to simulate the behaviour of the bed material (mean particle diameter of 110 μm) and the fine hydroxide powder (<10 μm), the density profiles of these two size fractions were defined separately. For the bed material, the radial distribution of solids is represented by a core-annulus model, where the internal circulation characteristic of the CFB is modelled by a dilute core region flowing upwards and a denser wall layer flowing downwards, as depicted in Fig. 3. These two regions have separate mass balances and exchange mass in every control volume, while chemical reactions are assumed to take place in the core region only. The axial density profile of the bed material follows the semi-empirical expression of Johnsson and Leckner (1995):

$$\rho_s(z) = [\rho_s(0) - \rho_s(Z_e) \exp(KZ_e)] \exp(-az) + \rho_s(Z_e) \exp(K[Z_e - z]). \quad (7)$$

The values of a and K are given by:

$$a = 4u_t/u \quad (8)$$

$$K = 0.23/[u - u_t]. \quad (9)$$

The solid density at the height of the exit opening, $\rho_s(Z_e)$, is estimated using the linear relation proposed by Ylätaalo et al. (2012):

$$\rho_s(Z_e) = c_{exit} \rho_{s,pn} \frac{u - u_t}{u_{pn} - u_t} \quad (10)$$

where u_{pn} is $15u_t$ and $\rho_{s,pn} = m_{s,bm}/V_{tot}$. Since the total mass of bed material in the reactor $m_{s,bm}$ is a state variable, it must equal the total mass of bed material defined by the density profile:

$$m_{s,bm} = \sum_i \rho_s(z_i) V_i \quad (11)$$

When combined with Eq. (7), this yields the density of solids at the bottom of the reactor:

$$\rho_s(0) = \frac{m_{s,bm} - \rho_s(Z_e) \sum_i V_i [\exp(K[Z_e - z_i]) - \exp(KZ_e) \exp(-az_i)]}{\sum_i V_i \exp(-az_i)} \quad (12)$$

The mass flow of solids exiting the reactor is estimated based on the solid density, gas velocity, and cross-sectional area near the exit opening of the reactor, as given by the empirical correlation proposed by Ylätaalo et al. (2012)

$$q_{m,circ} = c_{circ} A_c u_g \rho_{s,bm}^n, \quad (13)$$

The density profile of char is calculated in the same way, but due to its different material density and particle size as well as separate fitting parameters, it usually yields a different profile.

The fine powder, unlike the other solids, is assumed to be fully entrained by the gas flow. Since the powder injected is very fine (<10 μm),

Fig. 1. Illustration of the CaL model with injection of fine $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ powder.

Fig. 2. Flowchart of the 1.5D reactor model.

Fig. 3. Mass balances of the solid and gaseous phases of element i .

Table 1
Combustion reactions.

Equation	$\Delta H_{298\text{ K}}$ [kJ/mol]	Gas	k_0	a_1	a_2	a_3	a_4	T_e	Ref.
$4\text{NH}_3 + 5\text{O}_2 \longrightarrow 4\text{NO} + 6\text{H}_2\text{O}(\text{g})$	-906.2	NH_3	1.9×10^9	0	0.86	1.04	0	19 655	Johnson (1979)
$\text{H}_2\text{S} + 1.5\text{O}_2 \longrightarrow \text{SO}_2 + \text{H}_2\text{O}(\text{g})$	-518.2	H_2S	2.8×10^9	0	1.074	1.084	0	18 956	Leveson (1997)
$\text{CO} + 0.5\text{O}_2 \longrightarrow \text{CO}_2$	-283.0	CO	7.3×10^{14}	0	1	0.25	0.5	34 745	Yetter et al. (1986)
$\text{CH}_4 + 2\text{O}_2 \longrightarrow 2\text{H}_2\text{O}(\text{g}) + \text{CO}_2$	-802.3	CH_4	3.6×10^{11}	-1	1	1	0	15 700	Vilienskii and Hezmalian (1978)
$\text{C}_2\text{H}_4 + \text{O}_2 \longrightarrow 2\text{CO} + 2\text{H}_2$	-273.5	C_2H_4	2.2×10^3	2	1	1	0	14 394	Lee et al. (1993)
$\text{H}_2 + 0.5\text{O}_2 \longrightarrow \text{H}_2\text{O}(\text{g})$	-241.8	H_2	1.6×10^9	-1.5	1.5	1	0	3430	Vilienskii and Hezmalian (1978)

the slip velocity between gas and solids is negligibly small, and the mass flow of solids carried to the next element can be approximated by:

$$q_{m,i} = A_{c,i} u_{g,i} \rho_{s,i} \quad (14)$$

Closing the mass balance of the fine solid fraction yields the derivative of the density of fine solids in element i :

$$\frac{d\rho_{s,i}}{dt} = \frac{dm_{s,i}}{V_i dt} = \left[\sum_{in} q_{m,i} - \sum_{out} q_{m,i} + \sum_{reaction} r_i \right] / V_i \quad (15)$$

While the approach described assumes the two size fractions to be entirely independent of each other, some interaction would be expected, particularly in the context of clusters of larger particles dragging fine particles in their wake. However, since the $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ is injected in the dilute upper region of the reactor where the concentration of clusters is low and the solid phase consists mainly of dispersed particles, the frequency with which fine particles are dragged down by clusters is likely to be significantly smaller than it would be closer to the bottom of the reactor. Additionally, since the average velocity of solids in entrained flow is greater than that of the larger particles, the proposed method yields a conservative estimate of the residence time of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ in the reactor.

2.1.2. Species and reactions

The model incorporates 5 solid species (CaO , CaCO_3 , CaSO_4 , and $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$, while inert species are represented by SiO_2), 13 gaseous species (O_2 , N_2 , CO_2 , H_2O , NH_3 , H_2S , CO , CH_4 , C_2H_4 , C_7H_8 , H_2 , NO , and SO_2), and char. Rates of the reactions needed to model the carbonator and calciner are defined by kinetic expressions available in the literature. The decomposition of fuel into char and volatiles depends on the proximate and ultimate analyses of the fuel. The submodel used to determine the fuel decomposition is presented by Myöhänen (2011). The combustion rate of char is given by Basu (2006). The expressions for homogeneous combustion reaction rates can be written as:

$$r_{Gas,i} = k_0 T_i^{a_1} \exp(-T_e/T_i) C_{Gas,i}^{a_2} C_{\text{O}_2,i}^{a_3} C_{\text{H}_2\text{O},i}^{a_4} M_{Gas} V_i \quad (16)$$

where the values of k_0 , a_1 , a_2 , a_3 , a_4 , and T_e are as given in Table 1. Expressions for heterogeneous reactions are summarised in Table 2.

While several papers have published kinetic coefficients for the carbonation rate of CaO obtained by calcining limestone (CaCO_3), CaO derived by dehydrating $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ is known to be more reactive (Li et al., 2016). Arias et al. (2022a) found the combined dehydration-carbonation reaction of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ to be kinetically limited by the dehydration step under the conditions studied (300–650 °C, 2–25 kPa $_{\text{CO}_2}$). However, the carbonation reaction is known to be a first-order reaction with respect to the difference ($C_{\text{CO}_2} - C_{\text{CO}_2,\text{eq}}$) at partial pressures below 10 kPa (Grasa et al., 2009; Sun et al., 2008), and as the CO_2 concentration approaches equilibrium, the carbonation step is expected to slow down to the point of becoming the kinetically limiting step. The kinetic rate constant used in this work for the carbonation of CaO obtained by dehydrating $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ was determined from the results of a drop tube experiment (Arias et al., 2022b).

2.2. La Pereda model

A steady state measured at the 1.7 MW $_{\text{th}}$ La Pereda pilot plant (Arias et al., 2018) was used as a starting point for the simulations. The carbonator and calciner are both 15 m tall and have inner diameters

of 0.65 m and 0.75 m, respectively. Both reactors are refractory lined, and the carbonator is cooled by four bayonet tubes that hang from the top of the reactor. Each loop seal is connected to both reactors, which allows part of the solids to be internally circulated, i.e., recirculated back to the same reactor they came from. This recirculation is done by adjusting the position of a mechanical valve in the loop seal that controls how the flow is split between the two outlet channels. A more detailed description of the facility can be found in Arias et al. (2013).

In the studied case, coal was fired in a mixture of CO_2 and O_2 . The carbonator was fluidised at a moderate superficial gas velocity of 3.4 m/s. The specifications of the gas flows are given in Table 3 and those of the fired fuel in Table 4.

While data was available for several process variables, mass and heat balances written using experimental data are rarely properly closed due to accuracy limitations in the measurement techniques available. Consequently, there are difficulties defining the true state of the system being reconstructed. For instance, accurately determining the circulation of solids from experimental data is challenging. Equating the amount of CO_2 removed from the gas to the amount of CaCO_3 formed in the carbonator yields:

$$E_{\text{CO}_2} F_{\text{CO}_2,\text{in}} = F_{\text{Ca}} [X_{\text{CaCO}_3,\text{out}} - X_{\text{CaCO}_3,\text{in}}] \quad (17)$$

However, difficulties related to measuring mass flows and compositions can result in deviations of 30% between the measured gas and solid sides of the carbon balance of the carbonator (Arias et al., 2013). Because of these uncertainties, the solid circulation rate is not solved from (17) and measured gas and solid compositions. Instead, it is estimated based on temperature measurements and steady-state heat balances, as done by Arias et al. (2013). The heat transfer to the bayonet tubes was calculated using the correlation for wing walls (Basu, 2006).

Determining the amount of char burned in the carbonator is difficult for similar reasons. An estimate could be obtained by closing the oxygen balance around the carbonator, but the precision of flow rate and gas concentration measurements appeared to be insufficient for conclusive results. For reference, the oxygen concentration measured at the carbonator outlet and the corresponding value calculated by assuming no char combustion were 10.2%-m and 9.7%-m, respectively. However, closing the balances of inert gaseous species showed relative deviations of around 10%, which suggests that measurement errors were of a similar magnitude. While it appears that little to no char combustion occurred, the possibility that some char burned in the carbonator cannot be entirely excluded.

The simulations consisted of three steps. In the first step, a model of the pilot operating under the same experimental conditions was built. The parameters were calibrated and validated against experimental data, and the validated model served as a base case that was modified to study the effect of the modifications made. In the next step, the carbonator temperature was reduced while aiming to maintain the calciner temperature constant. The resulting case was essentially a prediction of the state of the pilot under different operating conditions, and it had a significantly different carbon capture efficiency even without the hydroxide injection. In the final step, the $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ injection was added to the model, and its effect on the overall carbon capture efficiency of the plant and other process variables was studied. Finally, to study how char combustion affected the performance of the carbonator, these

Table 2
Sorbent reactions.

Reaction	Equation	$\Delta H_{298\text{ K}}$ [kJ/mol]	Ref.
Calcination	$\text{CaCO}_3(\text{s}) \longrightarrow \text{CaO}(\text{s}) + \text{CO}_2(\text{g})$	178.2	
	$r_{calc} = k_{calc} n_{\text{Ca}} M_{\text{CaCO}_3} X_{\text{CaCO}_3}^{0.67} (C_{\text{CO}_2,eq} - C_{\text{CO}_2})$		Fang et al. (2009b)
	$k_{calc} = c_{calc} 2057 \exp\left(-\frac{112400}{RT}\right)$		Martínez et al. (2012)
	$C_{\text{CO}_2,eq} = \frac{4.137 \times 10^{12}}{RT} \exp\left(-\frac{20474}{T}\right)$		Stanmore and Gilot (2005)
	$c_{calc} = 0.2$		
Carbonation	$\text{CaO}(\text{s}) + \text{CO}_2(\text{g}) \longrightarrow \text{CaCO}_3(\text{s})$	-178.2	
	$r_{carb} = k_{carb} n_{\text{Ca}} X_{\text{CaO}}^{0.1} M_{\text{CaO}} (X_{\text{CaCO}_3, \text{max}} - X_{\text{CaCO}_3})^{0.67} (C_{\text{CO}_2} - C_{\text{CO}_2,eq})$		Grasa et al. (2009) (adapted)
	$k_{carb, \text{CaCO}_3} = 0.3429 \exp\left(-\frac{2309}{T}\right)$		Grasa et al. (2009) (adapted)
	$k_{carb, \text{Ca(OH)}_2} = 95 \exp\left(-\frac{2309}{T}\right)$		Grasa et al. (2009), Arias et al. (2022b) (adapted)
Direct sulphation	$\text{CaCO}_3(\text{s}) + \text{SO}_2(\text{g}) + 0.5 \text{O}_2(\text{g}) \longrightarrow \text{CaSO}_4(\text{s}) + \text{CO}_2(\text{g})$	-324.1	
	$r_{dirs} = k_{dirs} m_s W_{\text{CaCO}_3} C_{\text{SO}_2}^{-0.9} C_{\text{CO}_2}^{-0.75} C_{\text{O}_2}^{0.001}$		Myöhänen (2011)
	$k_{dirs} = 0.01 \exp\left(-\frac{3031}{T}\right) A_{m, \text{CaCO}_3} M_{\text{CaCO}_3}$ $A_{m, \text{CaCO}_3} = 300 [\text{m}^2/\text{kg}]$		Myöhänen (2011) Myöhänen (2011)
Desulphation	$\text{CaSO}_4(\text{s}) + \text{CO}(\text{g}) \longrightarrow \text{CaO}(\text{s}) + \text{SO}_2(\text{g}) + \text{CO}_2(\text{g})$	219.2	
	$r_{desu} = k_{desu} m_s W_{\text{CaSO}_4} C_{\text{CO}}$		Myöhänen (2011)
	$k_{desu} = 0.005 \exp\left(-\frac{10000}{T}\right) A_{m, \text{CaSO}_4} M_{\text{CaSO}_4}$ $A_{m, \text{CaSO}_4} = 100 [\text{m}^2/\text{kg}]$		Myöhänen (2011) Myöhänen (2011)
Sulphation	$\text{CaO}(\text{s}) + \text{SO}_2(\text{g}) + 0.5 \text{O}_2(\text{g}) \longrightarrow \text{CaSO}_4(\text{s})$	-502.2	
	$r_{sulph} = k_{sulph} m_s W_{\text{CaO}} W_{\text{SO}_2} W_{\text{O}_2}$ $k_{sulph} = 4.0(-3.843T + 5640) \exp\left(-\frac{8810}{T}\right)$		Myöhänen (2011) Myöhänen (2011)
Dehydration	$\text{Ca(OH)}_2(\text{s}) \longrightarrow \text{CaO}(\text{s}) + \text{H}_2\text{O}(\text{g})$	109.2	
	$r_{dehy} = k_{dehy} n_{\text{Ca}} M_{\text{Ca(OH)}_2} X_{\text{Ca(OH)}_2}^{0.67}$ $k_{dehy} = 4359.0 \exp\left(-\frac{63200}{RT}\right)$		Arias et al. (2022a) Arias et al. (2022a)
Water-gas shift	$\text{CO}(\text{g}) + \text{H}_2\text{O}(\text{g}) \longrightarrow \text{H}_2(\text{g}) + \text{CO}_2(\text{g})$	-41.1	
	$r_{WGS} = k_{WGS} (C_{\text{CO}} C_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} - C_{\text{CO}_2} C_{\text{H}_2} / K_{WGS})$		Macak and Malecha (1978)
	$k_{WGS} = 2.78 \exp\left(-\frac{12560}{RT}\right)$ $K_{WGS} = 0.0265 \exp\left(-\frac{3956}{T}\right)$		Macak and Malecha (1978) Hejazi et al. (2017)

Table 3
Gas inlet conditions of the simulated Calcium Looping plant.

Gas inlet	q_m kg/s	T °C	W_{CO_2} m-%	W_{O_2} m-%	W_{N_2} m-%	$W_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ m-%	W_{SO_2} m-%
Carbonator, fluidising gas	0.355	137	20.8	5.6	70.5	3.0	0.0015
Carbonator, loop seal air	0.066	20	0	23.3	76.7	0	0
Calcliner, fluidising gas	0.568	31	66.2	33.8	0	0	0
Calcliner, loop seal air	0.111	20	0	23.3	76.7	0	0

Table 4
Specifications of the coal used in the study. AR = as received, DAF = dry and ash-free, VM = Volatile matter, FC = fixed carbon.

Proximate analysis, kg/kg, AR				Ultimate analysis, kg/kg, DAF					LHV, AR
Moisture	Ash	VM	FC	C	H	N	S	O	MJ/kg
0.1	0.126	0.229	0.545	0.905	0.048	0.017	0.011	0.019	27.11

three steps were repeated three times for different char combustion profiles: one where the char particles in the carbonator were of the same size as in the calciner (400 μm), another where the particles were significantly smaller (150 μm), and the last where char particles were numerically prevented from reaching the carbonator. The cases simulated in the study are shown in Table 5. In both cases with char, its flow to the carbonator was adjusted to result in a consumption rate of 2 g/s, or an increase of approximately 1%-m in the CO_2 concentration of the gas. This conveniently chosen value is large enough to highlight the effect of CO_2 formation, while still being reasonably close to the measured gas concentrations.

In the cooling step, one way to reduce the temperature of the carbonator was by increasing the cooling surface area in its freeboard, which increased the temperature differential between the top and

Table 5
Cases simulated in the study.

	Char combustion profile		
	None	400 μm	150 μm
Base case	1	1	1
Cooled case, additional cooling surfaces	1	1	1
Cooled case, increased internal circulation	1	-	-
Hydroxide injection, 3 flow rates and 7 elevations	21	21	21

bottom regions of the carbonator. To prevent the temperature of the calciner from decreasing, the fuel flow also had to be increased. This approach was used in most simulations, including all cases with hydroxide injection. A different approach was also examined, where the external circulation of solids between reactors was decreased by internally circulating part of the entrained solids. Decreasing the external circulation rate reduced the heat input into the carbonator while also reducing the heat duty required by the calciner to heat the circulating solids, causing the temperature of the calciner to increase and that of the carbonator to decrease. Attaining a temperature difference of 100 °C between the dense bed and the exit of the carbonator still required some additional cooling surface area, though less than in the first approach. As the heat

Fig. 4. Simulated temperature and pressure profiles of the carbonator (CB) and calciner (CC) compared with measured values.

Table 6

Parameters used in the simulations. IC = increased cooling, RC = reduced circulation.

Parameter	Carbonator	Calciner
X_{max} ; CaCO ₃ -/Ca(OH) ₂ -derived CaO [mol/mol]	0.15/0.7	–
Make-up flow [kg/s]	–	0.082
Fuel duty; base/IC/RC [MW]	–	1.9/1.98/1.83
Temperature decrease in cyclone; heat losses [°C]	35	35
Heat losses, walls [kW]	15	30
Material density; sorbent/char [μm]	3000/550	3000/550
Particle diameter, sorbent; coarse/fine [μm]	110/10	110/-
Particle diameter, char; coarse/fine [μm]	400/150	400/-
Exit density coefficient c_{exit}	0.2	0.45
Circulation coefficient c_{circ} ; with/without char	0.61/0.71	0.57/0.67
Circulation exponent η	0.8	0.8
Bayonet tube area; base/IC/RC [m ²]	5.7/8.7/7.2	–

required to heat the solids in the calciner decreased, the fuel input also had to be reduced to maintain a constant temperature in the calciner. The parameters used in the simulations are given in Table 6.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Model validation

The modelled temperature and pressure profiles of the validated model are presented in Fig. 4 together with measurement data (Arias et al., 2018) from the base case. The hottest part of the carbonator is the dense bed, which is where the hot solids coming from the calciner enter the carbonator and where carbonation is most vigorous, resulting in a temperature of 710 °C. The influence of the hanging bayonet tubes can be seen as a temperature gradient starting at 3 m above the grid and extending to the top of the reactor, where the solids exit the carbonator at a temperature of 640 °C. Conversely, the calciner is coolest at the bottom, where the colder solids coming from the carbonator are fed, and heat is consumed to calcine the carbonated sorbent. The heat generated by combustion raises the temperature from 880 °C to 915 °C over the first three metres of the reactor. The pressure profiles show that the carbonator operates with a dense bottom bed to maximise gas–solid contact, whereas the calciner has a much leaner bed since calcination is known to be fast at temperatures above 900 °C.

The compositions of the gas and solid phases at the outlet of each reactor are presented in Fig. 5. The carbonator reduces the CO₂

concentration of the flue gas from 21%-m to 4%-m, corresponding to a capture rate of 80%. The calciner is fluidised by a gas mixture emulating oxygen mixed with recirculated flue gases, which causes the gas leaving the reactor to consist mainly of CO₂. On the solid side, the rates at which ash and CaSO₄ form are slow in relation to the solid circulation rate and their mass fractions are essentially the same in both reactors. Calcination and carbonation in their respective reactors cause the CaCO₃ content to be the main difference between them. While the simulated and measured CaCO₃ content at the calciner outlet are in close agreement, a larger difference is evident in the CaCO₃ content of solids leaving the carbonator. If the measured solid balance were used to determine the carbon capture efficiency of the carbonator, it would yield a value smaller than 50%. This is an obviously incorrect result, as it is in stark disagreement with the gas phase measurement, but it illustrates the challenges related to closing heat and mass balances based on experimental data. Overall, the simulation results are in very good agreement with measurements, which indicates that the model is able to capture the phenomena of the system correctly and can thus be applied to the modelling of CaL systems.

3.2. Temperature control

Fig. 6 shows the temperature profiles of three different cases: the base case, the case with increased cooling surface area and fuel feeding, and the case where the carbonator is cooled by internally circulating solids. Adding cooling surfaces to the carbonator while increasing the mass flow of fuel into the calciner results in a cooler carbonator without significantly affecting the temperature level of the calciner. Similar exit temperatures at the carbonator were obtained by internally circulating part of the entrained solids, but the bed is slightly cooler since less heat is extracted in the freeboard, leading to a smaller temperature difference between the top and bottom parts of the reactor.

The heat balances of the two reactors are illustrated in Fig. 7. Since the reactors are modelled in steady-state conditions, the sum of positive and negative terms is always zero. Additionally, due to the interconnected nature of the reactors, the sensible heat carried by solids leaving one reactor is equal to the heat of solids entering the other. Smaller components, such as the sensible heat of the gas feed, heat conduction through the reactor and cyclone walls, and heat losses associated with the extraction of bottom ash in the calciner, were grouped and labelled ‘Other’. Comparing the heat balances of the carbonator in the base case

Fig. 5. Simulated gas and solid compositions at the outlet of the carbonator (CB) and calciner (CC) compared with measured values.

Fig. 6. Temperature profiles of the carbonator (left) and calciner (right) simulated for different cases.

and the case with increased cooling shows that the sensible heat flow of the solid stream entering the carbonator decreases by 20% with the additional cooling, despite the temperature of the calciner increasing slightly. The sensible heat decreases because cooling the carbonator affects the circulation rate of solids, which is predicted to decrease from 1.9 kg/s to 1.5 kg/s. As the temperature of the carbonator decreases, the gas velocity also decreases in accordance with the ideal gas law, which, in turn, reduces the rate at which particles are entrained. This connection between the carbonator temperature and the rate at which particles are elutriated indicates that merely cooling the carbonator may significantly reduce the flow of fresh sorbent, which could limit the amount of carbon captured. The carbon capture efficiency of the simulated cases will be discussed in more detail in the next section. In the case with internal circulation of solids, 17% of the solids leaving the carbonator were internally circulated, while the corresponding value for the calciner was 42%. The internal circulation of solids decreases the circulation flow rate from the calciner to the carbonator to 1.1 kg/s while keeping their bed inventories nearly unchanged. The reduced external circulation rate, in conjunction with an increased cooling surface area and reduced fuel flow, results in the carbonator being cooled without significantly affecting the temperature of the calciner.

Comparing the heat balances of the base and cooled cases may offer additional insight into these two methods that can be used to cool the

carbonator. Since the reactors are at steady state, the heat balances of both cases can be equated. After rearranging terms and by denoting with Δ the difference obtained by subtracting the value of the base case from the cooled case, the expression can be written as follows:

$$\Delta(Q_{s,in} - Q_{s,out}) - \Delta Q_{g,out} + \Delta Q_{Ca-reactions} - \Delta Q_{HT} + \Delta Q_{fuel} + \Delta Q_{other} = 0 \tag{18}$$

The differences between the base case and the cooled case are presented in Fig. 8. The sensible heat of the gas stream entering the reactors is constant, and the difference is always zero. The carbonator graphs show that when the carbonator is cooled by increasing the heat transfer area, the additional heat extracted by the heat exchanger is provided mainly by the gas stream, the circulating solids, and additional carbonation. The small increase of 10 °C in the temperature of the calciner in relation to the base case slightly raises fuel consumption. However, further adjustments to the operation of the calciner can bring its temperature closer to that of the base case. Meanwhile, increasing the internal circulation rate reduces the heat input of the carbonator in the same way as installing additional heat transfer surfaces. However, while increasing the cooling area increased the fuel consumption of the process, internally circulating part of the solids led to a decrease in

Fig. 7. Heat balances of carbonator (CB) and calciner (CC) in their base state and with additional fuel feeding and cooling surfaces installed.

Fig. 8. Difference between the heat balances of the base and cooled cases of the carbonator (CB) and calciner (CC).

the fuel duty to prevent the temperature of the calciner from rising. The lower temperature in the carbonator causes the cooling duty to decrease. Despite being presented as two alternatives, these two methods to cool the carbonator can, in principle, be applied simultaneously to different extents, thus enabling the design of solutions tailored to different process requirements.

3.3. Carbon capture efficiency

Gas measurements showed that 80% of the CO_2 flowing through the carbonator was captured in the base case. As shown in Table 7, the simulated efficiencies are also close to 80%. When the temperature of the carbonator is reduced, the model predicts that the carbon capture efficiency of the cooled cases will increase to around 90%. This increase in capture efficiency is entirely due to different operating conditions in the carbonator, as no $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ is yet injected. Even the case with internal circulation saw an increase in capture efficiency, from 82% to 94%—which is higher than the case cooled by additional heat transfer surfaces—despite the reduced flow of active sorbent to the carbonator. This, along with the fact that cases with lower bed temperatures reached higher capture rates, suggests that the circulation rate of solids was originally higher than necessary for efficient carbon capture and that the carbon capture rate was limited by equilibrium. However, the CO_2 -carrying capacity of the sorbent is known to decrease as the

Table 7
Carbon capture efficiencies. The range of efficiencies with the injection covers $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2/\text{CO}_2$ molar ratios 1–3.

	Carbon capture efficiency			
	Measured	No char	400 μm	150 μm
Base	79.7%	82.4%	81.1%	80.2%
Cooled, increased cooling	–	92.5%	91.0%	90.3%
Cooled, reduced circulation	–	93.9%	–	–
$\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ injection at 6 m	–	96.2–98.9%	95.3–98.8%	95–98.7%

carbonation temperature decreases (Criado et al., 2018), and since the model does not currently consider this phenomenon, the resulting carbon capture rate may be overestimated. On the other hand, the fact that carbon capture efficiencies as high as 96% have been measured at the La Pereda pilot under similar temperatures and external circulation rates (Diego and Arias, 2020) partially supports the validity of these capture rates.

Fig. 9 shows that injecting $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ into the cooled carbonator further increases the carbon capture efficiency, with capture efficiencies as high as 99% being reached with a $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2/\text{CO}_2$ molar ratio of 3. The CO_2 flow in the denominator refers to the flow of CO_2 that exits the carbonator in the cases with increased cooling and no $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$, and as such is slightly different for different char combustion profiles. Char

Fig. 9. Overall CO₂ capture efficiency with varied Ca(OH)₂ injection heights and Ca(OH)₂/CO₂ molar ratios for three different cases: without char combustion in the carbonator, with combustion of char particles with a diameter of 400 μm at a rate of 2 g/s, and with combustion of char particles with a diameter of 150 μm at a rate of 2 g/s. The equilibrium line has been widened to cover its variation with the exit temperature of different cases.

combustion appears to play but a minor role at higher molar ratios, as the CO₂ formed is quickly captured by the excess Ca(OH)₂-derived CaO that is available. The importance of sufficient gas-sorbent contact time is made clear by the rate at which the carbon capture efficiencies decrease as the injection elevation is increased past 9 m, with an elevation of approximately 6 m appearing optimal. Injecting the Ca(OH)₂ at elevations below 6 m yields little to no further improvement. It should, however, be underlined that the model assumes that the material is evenly distributed within each control volume, and as such, the results presented here are based on the assumption that the Ca(OH)₂ powder is evenly distributed from the moment it is injected. A longer residence time in the reactor allows the powder more time to spread radially, and it may improve the performance of the process depending on the number of injection points and the design and implementation of the injection in general. In larger scale plants, the concentrations of both CO₂ and sorbent can be expected to vary significantly over the cross-sectional plane, and achieving an even distribution of sorbent on this plane will likely play a central role in the design of the carbonator. Achieving sufficient penetration of the Ca(OH)₂ injection in a deep and wide unit, for example, could pose a significant challenge.

Fig. 10 compares the CO₂ and carbonation profiles of the base case with a case where Ca(OH)₂ is injected at a molar ratio Ca(OH)₂/CO₂ of 3 and an elevation of 6 m above the grid. In both cases, the carbonation rate is highest close to the grid, where the concentration of both CO₂ and CaO is high. In the base case, the carbonation rate slows down as the CO₂ concentration decreases and approaches equilibrium. Starting from 3 m above the grid, the bayonet tubes decrease the temperature in the carbonator, reducing the equilibrium concentration of CO₂ and accelerating the carbonation rate. In the case with Ca(OH)₂, the equilibrium concentration in the dense bed is lower, and carbonation is allowed to progress further before being slowed down by the combined effects of equilibrium, reduced sorbent activity, and a lower suspension density. At the elevation of 6 m, a sharp reduction in CO₂ concentration is induced by the Ca(OH)₂ injection, and a clear decrease in the carbonation rate of the CaCO₃-derived CaO is observed. The reduced carbonation rate indicates that the Ca(OH)₂ injection inhibits the carbonation of the main sorbent by consuming the locally available CO₂, effectively replacing the CaCO₃-derived sorbent. As the Ca(OH)₂ is injected closer to the grid, an increasing share of the carbon captured

by the Ca(OH)₂ is carbon that would have been captured by the main sorbent if the hydroxide had been injected at a higher elevation. This growing inefficiency causes the overall CO₂ capture efficiency of the carbonator to plateau once the residence time of the Ca(OH)₂ reaches a sufficient level. It is worth noting that while not accounted for in the model, lowering the elevation of the Ca(OH)₂ injection is expected to increase the amount of Ca(OH)₂ dragged to the bottom of the reactor by back-mixing of larger particles. If this occurs to a sufficient extent, it could reduce the performance of the sorbent injected at the lower elevations. It is also worth noting that in CaL plants, the gas and solids are not separated at the top of the reactor, as in this model, but in the cyclone, thus extending the contact time between the gas and the sorbent.

3.4. Char combustion in the carbonator

The effect of char combustion is examined in more detail by comparing the CO₂ balance of two cases. These balances, obtained for fine (150 μm) and coarse (400 μm) char particles, are presented as 1D profiles in Fig. 11. The combustion profiles show that the char particle size has a clear effect on the shape of the profile: according to the correlation of Johnson and Leckner (1995), the concentration of coarse particles is larger at the bottom of the reactor. It follows that the rate of CO₂ formation is faster there, whereas the finer particles are more evenly spread and release a larger portion of the CO₂ above the dense bed. However, a significant amount – nearly two-thirds – of the CO₂ formed in the carbonator was produced by the water–gas shift reaction, which is clearly less sensitive to the size of char particles. The main difference is seen in the lower part of the carbonator, where the reaction gradually accelerates as CO is formed. A second, smaller peak is caused by the Ca(OH)₂ injection since both the capture of CO₂ by carbonation and the release of water vapour by dehydration increase the driving force of the water–gas shift reaction. However, it is evident that the effect of this phenomenon on the overall carbon capture efficiency is small. The carbonation profiles show that carbonation is barely influenced by the CO₂ formation profile. Owing to the excess sorbent and the proximity of the CO₂ concentration to equilibrium, any CO₂ source is partially counterbalanced by an increase in carbonation rate, stabilising the CO₂ concentration at the reactor outlet. Thus, when a sufficient amount

Fig. 10. CO₂ and equilibrium concentration profiles (a) and carbonation profiles (b) of the base case and the case with a Ca(OH)₂ injection at a molar ratio Ca(OH)₂/CO₂ = 3 and an elevation of 6 metres above the grid, with no char in the carbonator.

Fig. 11. Close-up of the CO₂ formation and consumption profiles for a case with a Ca(OH)₂ injection at an elevation of 6 m, a Ca(OH)₂/CO₂ ratio of 3 and average char particle sizes of 150 and 400 μm in the carbonator.

of Ca(OH)₂ is injected, the CO₂ concentration of the gas exiting the carbonator is not significantly affected by the formation of CO₂ at the rates studied.

4. Conclusions

A concept to increase the CO₂ capture efficiency of the calcium looping process was studied with a 1.5-dimensional reactor model. The simulation results indicate that merely decreasing the carbonator

temperature in preparation for the Ca(OH)₂ injection has a significant effect on the process, as the circulation rate of solids, reaction rates and equilibria are all affected. Whether the Ca(OH)₂ injection is able to sufficiently decrease the CO₂ concentration to reach an overall capture efficiency of 99% seems to depend mainly on a sufficient flow of Ca(OH)₂ being injected at an appropriate location, i.e., at a location that results in sufficient radial dispersion and a residence time of at least 2–3 s in the reactor. It should be noted that the cyclone can provide some additional contact time between the gas and the Ca(OH)₂.

Combustion of char transported from the calciner to the carbonator appears to only affect the carbon capture efficiency at low $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2/\text{CO}_2$ molar ratios. If the molar ratio is high enough, carbonation is limited mainly by equilibrium, and the effect of CO_2 formation in the freeboard of the reactor is mostly neutralised by the increased carbonation rate. As such, it appears that the carbon capture efficiency of the calcium looping process can be significantly improved by injecting $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ into the carbonator. However, the radial distribution of the $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ in the carbonator and the interaction between the bed material and the fine $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ powder are two aspects that are not considered by the 1.5D model used in this study. Future CFD studies could provide insight into the behaviour of the $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ particles in a CFB, while experimental results are needed before the validity of the assumptions made can be evaluated and the model validated.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Markus Secomandi: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Markku Nikku:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft. **Borja Arias:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Jouni Ritvanen:** Supervision, Software, Methodology, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Borja Arias has patent #EP 4 205 832 A1 pending to Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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